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Fagottini and Tenoroons: Small, Forgotten Giants

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Introduction

The research project “Fagottini and tenoroons—small, forgotten giants: Exploring the eighteenth- and nineteenth-century history, repertoire and usage of small-scale bassoons in performance and pedagogy” began its work at the Schola Cantorum Basiliensis in October 2017, and several members of the team presented its work at the IDRS conference in Granada in 2018. Funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation, the two-year pilot project is focusing on the documentation of surviving eighteenth- and nineteenth-century instruments in the form of an instrument catalogue, as well as the compilation of a repertoire list for small-scale bassoons.¹ Led by Dr. Thomas Drescher, director of the Schola Cantorum Basiliensis (University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, Academy of Music, Basel), the project team further consists of five historical bassoon performers and teachers: **Dr. Donna Agrell**, SCB and the Royal Conservatoire in The Hague, **Dr. Áurea Domínguez**, **Giovanni Battista Graziadio**, **Zoë Matthews**, and **Letizia Viola**.

Almost everyone has seen these small-scale instruments, found in the exhibitions of most major musical instrument museums, standing in the shadow of their larger counterparts. Generally viewed as curiosities, sparse explanations for their construction or descriptions of their use have been given. **James B. Kopp** dedicated a whole chapter to them in *The Bassoon* (2012), naming makers and possible performance works, while **Klaus Hubmann** (2011) proposed a theory about their functions.² But on the whole, relatively little research has been done on the subject and these instruments have yet to take their place in performance and pedagogy.

Small-scale bassoons would have continued to go unnoticed except for the fact that there are just too many of them to plausibly ignore; furthermore, it is evident that models were constructed by the most reputable eighteenth- and nineteenth-century woodwind makers and workshops throughout Europe, such as Denner, Grenser, Adler, and Savary.

A list of over one hundred surviving small-sized bassoons is currently included in our instrument catalogue, and more will surely be added.

Very few works scored for “fagottino” have been located, which is peculiarly disproportionate to the number of surviving instruments. The most important questions of how and where they were used have not yet been fully answered, and both Kopp and Hubmann have previously suggested that a re-examination of bassoon repertoire would be in order.

Confusing Terminology

Terminology describing small-scale bassoons in historical sources from the nineteenth century is confusing and contradictory and rife with regional differences: In 1840, **Josef Fahrbach** wrote about the various sizes in the bassoon family in his *Neueste Wiener Fagottschule, Op 17*, mentioning a full-size bassoon (“gewöhnliche Fagott”) and a tenor bassoon (“Tenor-Fagott”) playing a fifth higher than the first, adding that this is called “fagottino” in Italian. He also notes that a “Quart-Fagott” is pitched a fourth *lower* than the full-sized bassoon.³

Descriptions of the different-sized instruments are also offered in **Carl Almenröder**’s method from around the same time. He depicts a smaller instrument as being pitched a fourth, and not a fifth higher than the full-sized one. Almenröder also discusses terminology used for larger bassoons, pointing out that the “Quart-Fagott” cited in Zedler’s *Universal Lexicon* from the eighteenth century is actually a “Quint-Fagott”, a fifth lower than the full-scale bassoon.⁴ Checking the *Universal Lexicon*, we see that Almenröder is not entirely correct; two sorts of larger bassoons—transposing both a fourth and a fifth lower—and not one, are actually mentioned by Zedler.

Furthermore, in his treatise about orchestration from 1843–44, Hector Berlioz mentions an instrument pitched a fifth *higher*, explaining that the “basson quinte” is stronger and has a less “touching” sound quality than the “Corno anglais”. He also suggests that small bassoons might be advantageously used to soften the harshness heard in military music bands, implying that this was not yet common.⁵ The existence of other bassoon-like instruments (for example, “Russisches Fagott”, “Alto-Fagott” and a folded English horn) add to the overall confusion.

For practical reasons in this project, we have decided to use “fagottino” as a general name for small-scale bassoons, but also to specifically refer to those models pitched an octave higher than the full-size bassoon. “Tenoroon” is reserved in reference to models pitched a fourth or a fifth higher than the full-sized instrument.

Repertoire Classification

There are various examples of specific scoring for “fagottino” and “tenoroon”, such as those shown in Figures 1 and 2. The first, an excerpt from Nicola Porpora’s opera *Siface*, clearly lies well out-of-range for a full-scale eighteenth-century bassoon and is written in treble clef.⁶ The second, found in a four-part march, calls for a different instrument than that used in the bass line.⁷

Fig. 1. Nicola Antonio Porpora, *Siface*, Act III, Scena I (1730)

Fig. 2. Uri K. Hill, *Governor Sullivan's March* (1807–08)

Even though the actual range of the bassoon was always relatively large (up to three and a half octaves by the early nineteenth century), its highest register had specific, technical challenges.⁸ Berlioz warned that the notes from b^1 – e^2 were “hazardous” and advised composers not to write above b^1 .⁹

A key point seems to be that composers generally may not have consistently specified which size bassoon was intended to be used in their works. This would explain why some passages are out of the practical compass of a full-scale bassoon, or at least particularly awkward to execute in the keys written. Therefore, the logical solution proposed by both Hubmann and Kopp would be for a player to choose the most appropriate-sized instrument.¹⁰

Following this lead, we can present several examples that would be most suitable on smaller, transposing instruments. In Figure 3, an excerpt is displayed (one of many found in the opera *L'Isola disabitata* by Davide Perez), demonstrating the doubling of

the viola line by the bassoons in alto clef.¹¹ The first part ascends to d², an unlikely possibility for a bassoon from this period:

Fig. 3. Davide Perez, *L'Isola disabitata*, Palermo, 1748
(Overture, Andante molto, "Fagotti con le Viole")

In another more famous instance, a bassoonist from the late eighteenth century would have struggled with high-register fingerings in Beethoven's *Trio für Klavier, Flöte und Fagott in G-Dur, WoO37*, while attempting to execute the Adagio in an elegant and delicate manner equal to that of the flute. If considered that this work was composed for an amateur, a tenoroon in G would be an obvious choice, ascending only up to f² and using very simple fingering combinations.¹² A live performance of this movement may soon be viewed on our website.¹³

We have established a methodical system to analyze bassoon repertoire, considering aspects of playability such as range, keys, contexts, and technical and musical demands, and are using this tool to compile a list of suggested works for small-sized bassoons. The repertoire list will also include any new discoveries of scoring specifying small instruments, and will be regularly updated on our forthcoming website: www.historical-bassoon.ch.

An Instrument Catalogue

The other main goal of the pilot project is to publish a catalogue of as many surviving small-sized bassoons built between 1700 and 1914 as possible. The catalogue also

includes references to instruments taken from several historical documents, such as instrument advertisements and articles from period newspapers, maker's inventories, letters, and so forth.

In the era of digitalized information and “big data” where one can obtain museum catalogues, instrument pictures, inventories, and far more information than is humanly possible to process all in one click, the challenge of a modern humanities researcher lies in transforming the sort of raw information a catalogue offers into more philosophical thought, invoking cultural and historical insights into specific time periods. One of the main problems initially facing the fagottino project team was the lack of basic information about the instruments we were preparing to examine. The variety of terminology found in museums and archives challenges any interested person searching for basic data.

Even after exploring the first raw organology, proof of the historical value of those instruments was somehow undermined, or even missing. The next tasks were to prove that small-sized bassoons were not just anecdotes or toys, and to document their existence previous to the mid-twentieth century. The idea of creating a catalogue became a starting point, on the way to completing a too-often-forgotten chapter in the history of the bassoon. The ground was finally set, and after collecting ca. 100 entries of surviving fagottini and tenoroons in only the first year, we are ready for the instruments to begin to tell their own story.

The small-sized-bassoon catalogue will include a large amount of specific data about each instrument, as well as detailed photos of those examined. In the case of the most emblematic, a database with up to two hundred measurements, some with additional bore dimensions, is being constructed. These will include key measurements taken externally and internally; tone-holes angles, lengths, and positions; and bore diameters of the bassoon parts, as well as other details.

Detailed measurement data allows a profound comparison between makers' styles, underlining regional and historical differences in small-sized bassoons as well as analogs to larger, full-sized bassoons. From data already collected, the fagottini and tenoroons reveal themselves to be instruments with their own characteristics and features, going beyond being simply small versions of the bassoon.

Instrument Makers and Regions

As our catalogue shows, fagottini and tenoroons were built by the most renowned woodwind makers of the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. Instruments were being built in many different regions and therefore it is not possible to conclude if there was one unique, important fagottino nucleus.¹⁴

Fig. 4. FT 25, detail of key work from 14-key fagottino, Jean-Nicholas Savary de Jeune, Paris, 1827

Among Parisian makers we found examples by Martin Lot, Christophe Delusse, Dominique Porthaux, Frédéric-Guillaume Adler, and others. The famous Savary family also made numerous instruments. Both the elder, Savary père, from whom a tenoroon is preserved in the Philharmonie of Paris, as well as his son, Jean Nicholas Savary de Jeune, built numerous instruments. Figure 4 shows an extraordinary example by Savary de Jeune made in 1827. The 14-key fagottino possesses a particular key-work system, with a crossed- A^b key in the back of the butt joint and ivory reinforcement in several tone holes. This fagottino and other Savary tenoroons demonstrate outstanding craftsmanship, suggesting they were constructed for professional use.

Although the French musical center at that time was Paris, fagottino makers were distributed in other French-speaking regions as well, such as in Tours (François-Xavier Proff), Auch (Jacoby Fils.), and Strasbourg, where the famous Bühner & Keller makers were located.

Figure 5 depicts a 5-key fagottino stamped by Jacoby Fils in Auch, close

to the Spanish border in the south of France. This late eighteenth-century fagottino is made of boxwood instead of maple or fruit-tree wood; not a rare choice for small instruments, especially those from that period.

In Brussels, G.A. Rottenburgh, and in Mechelen, Jean Arnold Tuerlinckx also built several small-sized instruments. Furthermore, many instruments have survived that were made in the London area and other English cities by makers such as William Milhouse, Horwood & Astor, Charles Pace, Thomas Saxton, J. Collings, and John Blockley.

Fig. 5. FT17, 5-key fagottino, Jacoby Fils, Auch, ca. 1785

Fig. 6. FT11, 6-key tenoroon, Thomas Cahusac, London, 1789

Thomas Cahusac made the tenoroon in G shown in Figure 6. This instrument has an inscription with the date 1789 under the A^b key on the butt joint, with characteristically shaped keys of English instruments from the period.

Among makers from the Italian peninsula we find Bonaccorsi (Braga), Castlas (Torino), and Cristofaro Custode and De Rosa (Naples). From German cities, several outstanding instruments from the eighteenth century have survived, including those made by Johann Christoph Denner (Nuremberg), Johann Heinrich Eichentopf (Leipzig), Heinrich Carl Tölcke (Braunschweig), Johann Leiberz (Koblenz), Augstin

Fig. 7. FT29, 4-key fagottino,
Johannes & Georg Scherer,
Butzbach, ca.1764

and Heinrich Grenser (Dresden), as well the later nineteenth-century union of Grenser & Wiesner. Other makers of German origin are Schramme, Müller, Kuteruf, and I. Kraus.

In Butzbach, the Scherer factory was an important woodwind-making center in the eighteenth century. Johannes and Georg Heinrich Scherer built several fagottini, from which six have survived and are preserved in different museums. Figure 7 shows a 4-key Scherer fagottino in a very good state of preservation, currently in the Music Instrument Museum in Brussels. As discussed by Young, several craftsmen worked under the Scherer label, stamping their creations with their initials.¹⁵ The various Scherer fagottini found up to now share the characteristic of having different letters stamped in the wood, indicating how small bassoons were not made by just one maker, but several; a clear indication of the importance that small-sized bassoons had in the Scherer workshop.

By the turn of the nineteenth century, Viennese and nearby makers also built several instruments, such as those by

Wolfgang Küss, Kaspar Tauber, Magvini, Johann Stehle, Franz Scholl, Franz Wussinger, and Johann Joseph Merklein, whose tenoroon is shown in Figure 8. This 8-key tenoroon has the key system typical of bassoons made in Vienna in the nineteenth century, with two uniquely-placed wing-joint keys. On Merklein's instrument, as was common in bassoons from that region, the tone hole closer to the bocal well (C) is operated by the longer key, while the A-key is shorter and operated with the thumb pointing upwards. This is a completely different key placement than that found on German, French, and English instruments, where the two keys are inverted.

Remarks about Fagottino and Tenoroon

A close analysis of the instruments examined so far can also help determine crucial facts about the history of small-sized bassoon construction, such as what types were more common in different regions and time periods. As previously stated, the small-sized bassoons are classified as fagottini and tenoroons; the first sounds one octave higher than the full-sized bassoon, and the latter normally pitched in G or F.

As it is not always possible to try original instruments, it is sometimes difficult to determine what their transposing pitches are. Here measurements may play a significant role. The comparison in Table 1 (following page) shows some the external lengths (or standing lengths) taken from 35 instruments: 1) the bottom of the butt joint to the top of the bell; 2) the bottom of the butt joint to the top of the wing joint; 3) the total length in millimeters, derived by adding the two measurements. The instruments are chronologically ordered and give important information about geographical trends in instrument making and transposing pitch.

An analysis of this data defines, for instance, that the octave-higher fagottini (marked in grey) total lengths are between 1'000mm and 1'142mm, differentiating themselves from the tenoroons that can reach up to 1'642 mm.

As the instruments shown in Table 1 follow a chronological order, it is also possible to trace their geographical patterns, indicating that most of the smaller octave instruments were built in German

Fig. 8. FT19, 8-key tenoroon,
I. Merklein, Vienna, ca. 1835

ID NR	INSTRUMENT, MAKER, PLACE, DATE	Length - butt to bell	Length - butt to wing	TOTAL external length
FT14	3-key fagottino, Johann C. Denner, Nuremberg ca.1700	636	447.7	1083.7
FT7	3-key fagottino, Anonymous, ca.1730–1780	646.5	473.5	1120
FT23	4-key fagottino, Godfridus A. Rottenburgh, Brussels, ca.1760	667	448	1115
FT28	4-key fagottino, Johannes & Georg Scherer, Butzbach, ca.1760	639	459	1098
FT29	4-key fagottino, Johannes & Georg Scherer, Butzbach, ca.1764	642	464	1106
FT20	4-key fagottino, Müller, Germany, ca.1770	647	467	1114
FT30	5-key fagottino, Johannes & Georg Scherer, ca.1760–78	641	460	1101
FT18	4-key tenoroon, I. Kraus, Germany, ca.1775	764	589	1353
FT9	4-key tenoroon, John Blockley, Leicestershire, ca.1780	830	637	1467
FT4	4-key fagottino, Anonymous, ca.1780	641	463	1104
FT32	4-key fagottino, Heinrich C. Tölke, Braunschweig, ca.1780	647		
FT13	7-key fagottino, Christophe Delusse, Paris, ca.1783	626	418.5	1044.5
FT17	5-key fagottino, Jacoby Fils, Auch, ca.1785	636	440	1076
FT11	6-key tenoroon, Thomas Cahusac, London, 1789	837	641	1478
FT33	4-key fagottino, Jean A. Tuerlinckx, Mechelen, ca.1795	644	466	1110
FT3	4-key fagottino, Anonymous, Austrian Empire, ca.1800	635	471	1106
FT12	7-key fagottino, Castlas, Turin, ca.1800	599	400 / 373	999 / 972
FT16	5-key fagottino, Heinrich Grenser, Dresden ca.1800	669.3	472.8	1142.1
FT22	5-key tenoroon, François-Xavier Proff, Tours, ca.1800	716	563	1279
FT21	9-key tenoroon, Dominique A. Porthaux, Paris, ca.1808	937	642	1579
FT24	5-key tenoroon, Savary pere, Paris, ca.1810	762	551	1313
FT6	8-key tenoroon, Anonymous, Austrian Empire, ca.1815	840	563	1403
FT8	6-key tenoroon, Georg Astor & Horwood, London, ca.1815	890	680	1570
FT10	7-key fagottino, Bonaccorsi, Barga, ca.1815	630.5	435.5	1062.9
FT31	6-key tenoroon, Kaspar Tauber, Vienna, ca.1815	875	586	1461
FT34	5-key tenoroon, Jean A. Tuerlinckx, Mechelen, ca.1820	977	681	1658
FT15	6-key fagottino, H. Grenser & S. Wiesner, Dresden, ca.1824	670	449.5	1119.5
FT25	14-key fagottino, Jean-Nicholas Savary de Jeune, Paris, 1827	645	425	1070
FT35	0-key unfinished fagottino, Joseph Dupré, Tournai, ca.1830	637.5	447	1084.5
FT1	11-key tenoroon, Frédéric-Guillaume Adler, Paris, ca.1835	940	662	1602
FT19	8-key tenoroon, I. Merklein, Vienna, ca.1835	952	663	1615
FT26	12-key tenoroon, Jean-Nicholas Savary de Jeune, Paris, ca.1838	982	660	1642
FT2	13-key tenoroon, Frédéric-Guillaume Adler, Paris, ca.1840	947	630	1577
FT27	16-key tenoroon, Jean-Nicholas Savary de Jeune, Paris, 1841	980	658.5	1638.5
FT5	13-key tenoroon, Anonymous“S”, Paris, ca.1860	948.5	631	1579.5

Table 1. Instrument external lengths

regions in the mid-1700s. Smaller tenoroons (pitched in G) appeared in central Europe from France to England, existing together with smaller sizes arriving in England at the turn of the nineteenth century. Larger tenoroons pitched in F generally started to be built relatively late in the first quarter of the nineteenth century, and from Paris they rapidly started to be in fashion from Vienna to London.

Conclusion

The scope of this pilot project has proven to be larger and more significant than originally envisioned, and future projects will hopefully be able to address many open questions through thorough investigations of makers, performers, repertoire, and historical practice, as well as instrument re-construction. Meanwhile, the research team is continuing its compilation of the detailed documentation of surviving instruments, collecting measurements and other organological data, along with repertoire analysis and classification. The research results will not only alter our perceptions about the instruments of the historical bassoon family, but ultimately offer new sounds and colors to the tonal palette of performers.

Photo by Annelies van der Vegt

Prof. Dr. Donna Agrell teaches historical bassoons at the Schola Cantorum Basiliensis (University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, Academy of Music, Basel) and the Royal Conservatoire in The Hague, and plays bassoon in the Orchestra of the Eighteenth Century (Amsterdam).

Photo by Martin Chiang

Dr. Aurea Domínguez is the author of several scholarly publications such as Bassoon Playing in Perspective, (Helsinki, 2013), and co-author of Escribir sobre música (Barcelona, 2016). She is also a performer on historical bassoons.

Endnotes

- 1 URLs: <http://bit.ly/3169VrW>; and <http://p3.snf.ch/project-173363>
The project's own website will eventually go online at: www:historical-bassoon.ch.

- 2 James B. Kopp, *The Bassoon* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2012), Chapter 11, 222–28. Klaus Hubmann, ‘Hoch gestimmte Fagotte (Tenorfagotte) in der Musik vom späten 16. bis zum späten 18. Jahrhundert’, in: Christian Ahrens and Gregor Klinke (ed.), *Flöte, Oboe, Klarinette und Fagott: Holzbalsinstrumente bis zum Ende des 18. Jahrhunderts* (Tage Alter Musik in Herne 2008; München–Salzburg: Katzbichler, 2011), 78–84.
- 3 Josef Fahrbach, *Neueste Wiener Fagottschule, Op 17* (Vienna: Diabelli n.d. [1840]), 15. The larger “Quart-Fagott” is a very rare instrument, of which only several exist.
- 4 Carl Almenräder, *Vollständige theoretisch praktische Fagottschule* (Mainz: Schott, 1843), 1. See also: Johann Heinrich Zedler, *Grosses vollständiges Universal-Lexicon aller Wissenschaften und Künste 1731–1754*, 94.
- 5 Hector Berlioz, *Grand Traité d’Instrumentation et d’Orchestration Modernes* (Paris: Schonenberger, n.d. [1844]), 133.
- 6 Nicola Antonio Porpora, *Siface*, Act III, Scena I (Rome 1730, fol. 268r). [Manuscript autograph in the Library of the Brussels Royal Conservatoire.]
- 7 Uri K. Hill, *Gov. Sullivan’s march* (Publisher not indicated, United States, 1807– 08, monograph). Retrieved from the Library of Congress, www.loc.gov/item/2015560592/, accessed on July 30, 2018. Probably composed for and performed at an official event.
- 8 Donna Agrell, ‘Repertoire for a Swedish Bassoon Virtuoso: Approaching early nineteenth-century works composed for Frans Preumayr with an original Grenser & Wiesner bassoon’, PhD dissertation (Leiden, 2015). URL: <https://openaccess.leidenuniv.nl/handle/1887/36960>. See her reports about range and Frans Preumayr, 54–57; 97.
- 9 Berlioz (1844), 128.
- 10 Kopp (2012), 225. Hubmann (2011), 78–84.
- 11 Davide Perez, *L’Isola disabitata*, Palermo (1748). [Biblioteca del Conservatorio di musica S. Pietro a Majella (I-Nc): 30.4.5]
- 12 Kopp (2012). 225.
- 13 Ludwig van Beethoven, “Trio für Klavier, Flöte und Fagott”, WoO 37 (ca. 1786–90). A performance by Letizia Viola with tenoroon will be available soon at: www.historical-bassoon.ch, “A taste of Beethoven with tenoroon”.
- 14 Kopp (2012), 223–227. See Chapter 11: Kopp lists makers in various regions and times.
- 15 Phillip T. Young, “The Scherers of Butzbach” in *The Galpin Society Journal*, Vol. 39 (Sep. 1986), 112–24.